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THE REPRESENTATION AND REPRODUCTION OF GENDER ASYMMETRY IN LANGUAGE: A SOCIOCULTURAL APPROACH

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Abstract

This article examines gender as a sociocultural and linguistic construct and explores the role of language in the representation and reproduction of gender differences and stereotypes. Within the framework of the anthropocentric paradigm of modern linguistics, language is viewed as a cognitive and cultural instrument through which social reality is interpreted and constructed. The relevance of the study is обусловлена growing scholarly interest in the interrelation between language, thought, culture, and gender in the context of persistent gender asymmetry in contemporary society.

The aim of the study is to analyse gender not as a purely biological category, but as a socially and culturally determined phenomenon reflected in linguistic and communicative practices. The methodological framework is based on descriptive and interpretative approaches and includes elements of discourse and linguocultural analysis. The article discusses lexical, grammatical, and phraseological representations of gender stereotypes in different linguistic and cultural contexts.

Particular attention is paid to the androcentric character of language and culture, the linguistic mechanisms of gender representation, and the role of stereotypes in shaping social perceptions of masculinity and femininity. The study also addresses the theory of linguistic relativity, feminist approaches to language, and the concept of “doing gender” as a socially reproduced practice.

The findings suggest that language not only reflects existing gender relations but also contributes to their preservation and reproduction through culturally established norms, evaluative patterns, and communicative behaviour. The article concludes that gender is a dynamic sociocultural construct continuously shaped through language, culture, and social interaction.

Keywords: gender; language; sociocultural construction; gender stereotypes; androcentrism; gender asymmetry; gender linguistics; discourse; linguistic relativity

The emergence of the anthropocentric paradigm has led to a shift in linguistic discourse towards the human being and their place in the world and in culture. Language came to be defined as a creative instrument of consciousness, enabling humans to model and create reality. The intensive development of gender studies in recent years has been driven by this postmodernist conception of the humanities.

The relevance of this study stems from the growing attention in contemporary linguistics to the relationship between language, thought and socio-cultural factors, particularly gender, as well as the need to identify the mechanisms of linguistic representation and the construction of gender differences in the context of persistent gender asymmetry in society.

The aim of this study is to analyse gender as a sociocultural and linguistic construct, as well as to identify the role of language in the formation, representation and reproduction of gender differences and stereotypes.

The methodological framework of this study comprises descriptive and interpretative methods, elements of discursive and cross-cultural analysis, as well as an analysis of linguistic units (lexical, grammatical and phraseological) that represent gender stereotypes in various languages and cultures.

Gender relations permeate, in one way or another, all spheres of human activity. A person's sex is one of the most important existential and socially significant

characteristics, which determines their social, cultural and cognitive orientation in the world. Gender self-identification is among the cognitive resources of both the individual and society as a whole. Consequently, gender is the subject of study in many social sciences, including linguistics. Contemporary social science distinguishes between the concepts of ‘sex’ and ‘gender’. The former refers to the physiological characteristics of people, on the basis of which human beings are defined as male or female. Gender, however, encompasses psychological, cultural and social aspects. Gender studies examines the relationship between a person's biological sex and their cultural identity, psychological characteristics, social status, and behavioural strategies in the communicative process. Research shows that it is not biological sex, but socio-cultural norms that determine the psychological characteristics, behavioural patterns, activities and professions of women and men. Being a man or a woman in society does not simply mean possessing the corresponding anatomical characteristics; it means fulfilling certain culturally prescribed gender roles. In 1949, Simone de Beauvoir observed that one may be born with female physical characteristics, but it is a matter of becoming the social being that society defines as a ‘woman’. The same can be said of men.

Every society, based on a person's gender, imposes requirements to adhere to so-called ‘gender

norms' – to fulfil certain social roles, behavioural standards, and so on. From the moment of birth, a person becomes subject to the influence of the gender system. Even the colour of clothes and sets of toys are chosen according to the child's gender. During upbringing, the family, the education system and culture as a whole instil the necessary gender norms into children's minds. We are all familiar with traditional forms of gender differentiation, based on the notion that a 'real man' must be strong, independent, self-reliant and emotionally reserved, whilst a 'real woman' must be dependent, weak, caring and emotional.

Gender differences are not merely created; they are endlessly reproduced. Sigmund Freud believed that gender is destiny. Feminists have proposed their own understanding of gender as a performance. Indeed, it must be acknowledged that, consciously or unconsciously, all people are constantly engaged in 'the performance of presenting themselves as men or women' [Pushkareva 2007:177]. Moreover, this process unfolds in such a way that this 'game' seems to a person to be inherently natural. Every action or behaviour can be perceived as an expression and affirmation of one's belonging to a particular gender, as behaviour appropriate to a given situation—whether feminine or masculine—and a corresponding reaction is expected in return, one characteristic of a particular era, culture and society. Gender is not something given by nature. Let us recall the very apt English term 'doing gender', which reflects an important property of gender – the ability to be created and reproduced. This is a systemic characteristic of social relations, which cannot be rejected or discarded. Speaking of the social construction of gender, A.A. Temkina compares it to the cloak of the centaur Nessus. According to the myth, Heracles put on a poisoned cloak. When the poison began to take effect, he tried to get rid of it, but the cloak had fused with him and could only be torn off along with his skin. Breaking free from gender identity is the same as tearing off Nessus's cloak. "Recognising that gender is culturally determined, institutionalised and ritualised also leads to the recognition that it is a social construct, manifesting itself differently across various cultural and linguistic communities at different stages of their development. All this allows us to approach the phenomena of masculinity and femininity not as immutable natural givens, but as dynamic, changeable products of the development of human society, susceptible to social manipulation and shaping" [Kirilina 2005: 26].

Different cultures have adopted various forms of gender distinctions. In most cultures, the 'masculine' is identified with spirit, activity, strength, independence, emotional restraint, rationality and light. The 'feminine', on the other hand, is associated with matter, chaos, nature, emotionality, passivity, weakness and dependence. Men and women are assigned opposing social roles. The following binary oppositions, attributed to men and women, are usually distinguished: 1) logic – intuition; masculinity is associated with logic, whilst femininity is associated with intuition (S. N. Bulgakov; N. A. Berdyaev; V. F. Ern; V. Solovyov; P. A. Florensky; V. V. Rozanov et al.); 2) conscious-

ness – unconsciousness, expressiveness; there is a stereotypical belief that female sensuality and emotional expressiveness distinguish her from men with their measured, conscious nature; 3) power – submission; traits such as docility, devotion and self-sacrifice are considered feminine. As Rozanov writes, a man is attributed the right to command a woman, whilst a woman's right is to receive, in return for her love, a manly and strong protector. F. Nietzsche believed that a man's happiness is called 'I want!', whilst a woman's happiness is 'He wants!' 4) independence, individuality – collectivity; it is considered that women prioritise interpersonal relationships; they are democratic and responsive, whilst men are more independent, dominant and authoritarian; 5) order – chaos; N. A. Berdyaev viewed the masculine principle as the principle of order, since the masculine spirit brings meaning, shapes and organises; 6) activity – passivity; Aristotle's theory, according to which strength, activity and movement are characteristic of the masculine principle, whilst women represent passive matter, persisted right up to the modern era; 7) strength – weakness; it is believed that men and women are distinguished by the manifestations of strength in their personalities; 8) inconstancy, radicalism – constancy, conservatism; there is a prevailing belief that, unlike men, women are more constant. (Although observations show that neither in a biological nor a psychological sense does pure masculinity or femininity exist, and that every personality combines the biological and psychological traits of both sexes ('androgynous personality', according to Sandra Bem's theory)).

Gender inequality has existed throughout history. For centuries, women were perceived as chaotic, irrational (Aristotle), sensual (Kant) or immoral (Schopenhauer) beings. Even at the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries, some scholars seriously believed that women were the lowest rung on the evolutionary ladder. The origins of this attitude are as ancient as the history of humanity itself – Adam has still not forgiven Eve for the Fall. Analysing the image of women throughout history, one researcher, J. Hunter, concludes that, on the whole, this is an image of inferiority, and that the process of women's emancipation has, since ancient times, been associated with destructive social consequences. *Cherchez la femme* – 'look for the woman', for she is the source of all misfortune. Social norms change over time, yet gender asymmetry (with the balance tilted towards the male half) remains. Feminism has made a significant contribution to the formation of the modern model of humanity. Although the term 'feminist' itself is still viewed negatively by society. As V. A. Maslova writes, in the popular consciousness, a 'feminist' is something halfway between a 'lesbian' and a 'nymphomaniac'. Since the 19th century, women have been actively fighting for social and political equality. Over the past few decades, a large number of works analysing gender issues have appeared. Feminist language critics write extensively about the androcentrism of modern culture, arguing that the world is organised in such a way that everything masculine is understood as the norm, whilst everything feminine is seen as a pathol-

ogy. ‘Androcentrism is a deeply rooted cultural tradition; it reduces universal human subjectivity to a single masculine norm and presents it as universal objectivity. It is a view of the world from a male perspective and the presentation of masculine normative ideas and attitudes as universal social norms and attitudes. Language, reflecting public consciousness, fixes the male worldview’ [Islamova 2015: 1384].

Language plays an important role in reproducing the androcentrism of culture; it does not merely reflect the gender differentiation existing in society, but, moreover, is capable of constructing gender differences itself. The renowned linguist and feminist Robin Lakoff noted that ‘language uses us just as much as we use it’ [Lakoff 1975: 3]. Gender linguistics bases its approach to language on the Sapir–Whorf hypothesis of linguistic relativity, according to which language determines human thought, worldview, culture and social behaviour. According to Whorf, ‘our linguistically determined mental world not only corresponds to our cultural ideals and attitudes, but even draws our subconscious processes into its sphere of influence and imbues them with certain characteristic features’. [Alpatov 1998]. On the basis of this hypothesis, proponents of philosophical linguistics argue that all languages functioning in patriarchal and post-patriarchal cultures are masculine languages and are constructed on the basis of a masculine worldview. ‘Language captures a worldview from a male perspective; therefore, it is not only anthropocentric (human-centred) but also androcentric (male-centred): language creates a worldview based on a male perspective, from the standpoint of a male subject, where the female appears primarily as an object, as the Other, the Stranger, or is ignored altogether, which is the essence of the feminist ‘criticism’. [Kirilina 2001].

Linguistic data is one of the primary sources of information regarding the nature and dynamics of gender formation as a product of culture and social relations. Language provides a key to understanding the mechanisms by which gender identity is constructed. For example, feminine nouns are most often derived from masculine ones. In doing so, they acquire a negative connotation. As N. M. Gabrielyan notes, the view of women as a kind of derivative of men is quite clearly evident even from a cursory analysis of certain grammatical forms. As an example, she cites words denoting professions: in the Russian language, the ‘feminine’ variants of professional titles, when compared to their ‘masculine’ counterparts, acquire a stylistic inferiority. In essence, grammar in this case acts as a means of suggestion, of implanting deep within the consciousness the idea that a woman engaged in the professions listed above is, as it were, a parody of a man [Gabrielyan 1993: 71]. In German-speaking countries, this led to mass protests, and since the late 1970s, legislation has been enacted to introduce gender-neutral professional titles for women in official documents. Observations suggest that there is currently a trend in the English language towards a shift in the perception of gender roles. Both sexes are frequently described as ‘working’, ‘professional’, ‘high-achieving’ and ‘powerful’. There is

also a trend towards describing women as ‘self-confident’, ‘self-assured’, ‘successful’, and so on. Researchers have noted that in many cultures, the use of masculine terms in relation to women significantly elevates their status (a man’s mind, a man’s touch, a man’s character), whereas feminine terms and comparisons applied to men carry a clearly negative connotation (chatty, flirtatious, capricious, hysterical, curious, like a woman).

Gender relations are enshrined in language in the form of culturally conditioned stereotypes, which leave their mark on human behaviour (including speech). For example: «Мужнин грех за порогом остается, а жена все домой несет» (‘A husband’s sins remain outside the threshold, but a wife brings everything home’); «Муж - глава семьи» (‘The husband is the head of the family’); «Бабе дорога от печи до порога» (‘A woman’s path is from the stove to the threshold’); «Все бабы дуры» (‘All women are fools’); «Волос долгий, ум короткий» (‘Long hair, short wits’); «Бабы умы разоряют дома» (‘Women’s minds ruin homes’) and so on. Gender stereotypes are among the most persistent and widespread, and can be no less destructive than racial and ethnic stereotypes (e.g., due to existing stereotypes, it is difficult for a woman to realise her potential in politics or business). Research into the characteristics of communication shows that different strategies of verbal behaviour in men and women develop on the basis of stereotypes. For example, common characteristics of female speech behaviour have been identified: the use of diminutive suffixes, polite forms, a lack of dominance, the ability to listen to the other person, and so on. Male speech, on the other hand, is characterised by aggressiveness, the use of non-standard vocabulary, dominance, and so on.

Gender is one of the factors through which the speaker’s social identity is constructed in communication. Undoubtedly, it interacts with other factors, namely status, age, social group, and so on. There is as yet no unified concept for the study of gender in communication within the academic community. One of the best-known works in this field is Deborah Tannen’s “You just don’t understand. Women and men in conversation”. Tannen analyses communication breakdowns between people of different genders and explains them by the different demands society places on men and women, as well as the specific nature of socialisation during childhood and adolescence, when communication takes place predominantly within same-sex groups. Under the influence of these factors, women and men develop different behavioural motives, communication strategies and tactics. For example, men’s speech behaviour is generally aimed at achieving and maintaining independence and high status. Society, however, expects something entirely different from women – a non-confrontational approach, gentleness, tolerance, compliance and emotionality. According to D. Tannen’s theory, such differences lead to variations in communication goals and in the interpretation of utterances. Men and women may interpret their conversation partner’s words differently and be guided by different motives. It should also be borne in mind that every culture has different communication

traditions for men and women. For example, during a feast, the floor is usually given to men. Drawing on research data, D. Tannen developed the theory of genderlect. Genderlect refers to the socially and culturally conditioned characteristics of communication between men and women. Although this theory of genderlect has not gained universal acceptance in linguistics, it is nevertheless worth acknowledging that D. Tannen's model helps to clarify many issues in gender studies.

In his work "Linguistic Representation of Gender", N. Kurilovich rightly points out that: 'masculinity and femininity are not, in fact, opposites, but dialectically interrelated categories; nor are they something fixed, given once and for all. On the contrary, they are social processes. Language is not merely a mirror of gender; it helps to constitute it. In other words, it is one of the ways in which gender is prescribed. Gender is not some unchanging state of human existence. Gender is, first and foremost, a set of practices and actions. Gender is performed by people, and in different situations in different ways. Drawing a linguistic analogy, one might say that gender is not a noun, but a verb.

Thus, gender is a sociocultural phenomenon, and people exist in a world of standardized ideas and stereotypes imposed by society, culture, and language. They are subject to a system of gender differences created and accepted within a given culture. Gender differences are not simply created, but are endlessly recreated. Language reflects the social and cultural specifics of a society, so an analysis of linguistic constructions provides insight into the role gender plays in a given culture, how perceptions of gender norms change over time, how gender stereotypes are reflected in language, how masculinity and femininity are understood in different languages and cultures, and so on. Research shows that sexism lies not so much in language as in people's consciousness. Language not only reflects existing gender differentiation in society, but, moreover, is capable of directly constructing gender differences.

References:

1. Alpatov, V. M. *History of Linguistic Schools/Study Guide*. Moscow: 'Languages of Russian Culture', 1998. pp. 222-256. (in Russian)
2. Burukina, O. A. *The Gender Aspect of Translation*. [Electronic resource]. URL: <http://www.auditorium.ru/> (in Russian)
3. Chikvaidze, A. A. Constructing Gender Differences in Culture and Language // *Actual Problems of Germanic, Romance, and Russian Studies*. Proceedings of the Annual International Conference. Yekaterinburg, 2022. Pp. 18–24. (in Russian)
4. Chikvaidze, A. A. Issues of Gender in Culture and Language // *Information and Communication Technologies in Russian Studies: Current State and Perspectives*. Proceedings of the III International Virtual Scientific-Practical Conference. Yerevan: Limush, 2010. Pp. 170–174. (in Russian)
5. *Dictionary of Gender Terms* / Ed. by A. A. Denisova. Moscow: Information XXI Century, 2002. 256 p. [Electronic resource]. URL: <http://www.owl.ru/gender/index.htm> (in Russian)
6. Gabrielyan, N. M. *The Emerging Atlantis (Meditation on the Theme of Feminism) // Social Sciences and Modernity*. 1993. No. 6. [Electronic resource]. URL: <https://a-z.ru/women/texts/atlanditar.htm> (in Russian)
7. Islamova, F. A. On Gender Relations in Language // *Bulletin of Bashkir University*. 2015. Vol. 20. No. 4. Pp. 1383–1384. (in Russian)
8. Kirilina, A. V. *Gender: Linguistic Aspects*. Moscow: Institute of Sociology, Russian Academy of Sciences, 1999. [Electronic resource]. URL: http://www.ahmerov.com/book_1030.html (in Russian)
9. Kirilina, A. V. 'The Relationship between Language and Gender in the History of Linguistics' // *Theory and Methodology of Gender Studies*. Moscow: MCGI-MVSHEN-M.FF, 2001. pp. 369-416. (in Russian)
10. Kirilina, A. V. Gender Studies in Linguistic Disciplines // *Gender and Language*. Moscow State Linguistic University; Laboratory of Gender Studies. Moscow: Languages of Slavic Culture, 2005. Pp. 7–32. (in Russian)
11. Kirilina, A. V. *The Potential of the Gender Approach in Anthropocentric Studies of Language and Communication*. [Electronic resource]. URL: <http://www.gender-cent.ryazan.ru/kirilina1.htm> (in Russian)
12. Kurilovich, N. *Linguistic Representation of Gender*. [Electronic resource]. URL: http://en-vila.iatp.by/g_centre/another3/art11.html (in Russian)
13. Lakoff, R. *Language and Woman's Place*. New York: Harper & Row, 1975. 83 p.
14. Maslova, V. A. *Linguoculturology*. Moscow, 2004. (in Russian)
15. Prosekova, M.N., & Stebunova, E.I. Gender Aspects in Contemporary Linguistics // *Bulletin of Tyumen State University* – 1993, No. 6. pp. 110–116. [Electronic resource]. URL: https://elib.utmn.ru/jspui/bitstream/ru-tsu/32981/1/vestnik-TyumuGU_2007_2_110_116.pdf?ysclid=mppq4qxr7349833926 (in Russian)
16. Pushkareva, N. *Gender Theory and Historical Knowledge*. Saint Petersburg: Aleteya, 2007. 496 p. (in Russian)
17. Voychenko, V. M. *The Reflection of Gender Stereotypes in Language and Culture*. [Electronic resource]. URL: <http://cyberleninka.ru/article> (in Russian)